

FORMULA TO KNOW IF A NUMBER IS PRIME OR NOT

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$2^{p-1} * 2^p \bmod p = 2$ Than p Is a Prime Number

$2^{p-1} * 2^p \bmod p \neq 2$ Than p Is not a Prime Number